

THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING OF SAFFIL REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

G. Durrant* and V.D. Scott**

*Oxford Centre for Advanced Materials and Composites
Department of Materials, University of Oxford, Oxford OX1 3PH, UK

**School of Materials Science, University of Bath, Bath BA2 7AY, UK

ABSTRACT

The upset forging of aluminium (LM0) and aluminium-7% silicon alloy (LM25) reinforced with Saffil fibres has been investigated. At room temperature, the flow stress of LM25 and LM0 reinforced with 9% Saffil fibre was similar but significantly greater than unreinforced LM0. The result is discussed in terms of load transfer from matrix to fibre and dislocation pile-ups at hard inclusions. With higher forging temperatures, the flow stress of LM25 and LM0 composite approached that obtained for unreinforced LM0 as a result of increased rates of dislocation climb and dynamic recovery, which accords with TEM observations. The composite materials were found to have limited workability and this is related to the formation of voids between the ends of broken fibres. The flexural modulus of LM0 and LM25 composites was reduced by ~20% after room temperature forging as a result of severe fibre breakage and porosity (more than 1.0%). Forging at temperatures close to the melting point of the metal resulted in flexural modulus values which were similar to those for as-received composite; this is attributable to markedly reduced fibre breakage and smaller amounts of porosity.

Keywords: Forging, Composite, Aluminium, Alumina

1. INTRODUCTION

Although the specific mechanical properties of aluminium alloys can be significantly improved by reinforcement with short alumina fibres, the fabrication of the final component presents a number of difficulties, particularly as a result of their limited machineability. Thus near-net shape thermomechanical processing techniques, such as extrusion, rolling and forging, are being investigated. Furthermore, with control of the processing parameters (temperature, strain and strain rate) mechanical properties may be enhanced as a result of preferential fibre alignment and changes in the matrix microstructure.

In this paper we present data regarding the upset forging of aluminium (LM0) and aluminium-7% silicon alloy (LM25) reinforced with Saffil fibres. Attention is focused on the behaviour of these materials during deformation, e.g. flow stress and workability, and on resultant microstructures and mechanical properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Material

Composites based upon commercially pure aluminium (LM0) were fabricated by a squeeze casting process with a Saffil fibre volume fraction of $\sim 20\%$ and $\sim 9\%$; these will be referred to as LM0/20 Saf and LM0/9 Saf. LM25 composite contained $\sim 20\%$ Saffil fibre (LM25/20 Saf) and was fabricated by gas pressure casting. The fibres in all MMCs had an approximately planar random alignment.

2.2. Forging Conditions

Cylindrical samples were machined from the composite billets and forged by compression in a 10 tonne Instron press. The temperatures used ranged from 20°C to 625°C for LM0 and from 20°C to 585°C for LM25 composite (the upper temperature being slightly above the Al-Si eutectic temperature of $\sim 577^\circ\text{C}$).

2.3. Flexural Modulus

Specimens $\sim 20\text{mm} \times 4\text{mm} \times 1\text{mm}$ were machined from the forged cylinders and tested at room temperature in four-point bending. A strain gauge was attached to the tensile surface of the test coupon.

2.4. Fibre Orientation

The orientation of fibres was evaluated from the ellipse formed when a fibre cuts a polished section of the composite. For a planar random array of fibres, the fibre orientation may be described by the distribution of in-plane angle and out-of-plane angle, see Figure 1. The cylindrical samples used for forging were cut such that the loading axis (compression direction) was perpendicular to the fibre planes (ie. parallel to the z axis in Figure 1). In-plane angle and out-of-plane angle were then established from sections cut perpendicular and parallel to the loading axis respectively.

2.5. Dislocation Density

Thin foils were prepared for transmission electron microscopy using a cold stage ion beam miller. During examination, the specimen was tilted to provide the maximum number of dislocations, thereby minimizing the number of dislocations invisible due to unfavourable diffraction conditions¹. The local foil thickness was measured by means of the contamination spot technique², and the dislocation density calculated. Since this technique tended to overestimate foil thickness, the measured density is expected to be an underestimate of the true value.

The techniques used to establish fibre aspect ratio and composite density have been reported in a previous paper³.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Forging Characteristics

Flow stress data were determined for unreinforced LM0 and LM25 metal and for LM0/9 Saf composite using a technique⁴ designed to eliminate the effects of friction between sample and platen. All tests were carried out with an average true strain rate of $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

True stress versus true strain curves are illustrated in Figure 2. At room temperature, significant work hardening was observed in all cases, with the rate of hardening being greatest for LM0/9 Saf, slightly less for LM25 metal, and lowest for LM0 metal. At higher forging temperatures, the rate of work hardening decreased until, at $\sim 300^{\circ}\text{C}$, no hardening was observed for any of the materials. Values of flow stress at a strain of 10% plotted as a function of forging temperature are illustrated in Figure 3. The data revealed that the addition of 9% Saffil fibres more than doubled the flow stress of LM0 over the entire temperature range, but that the flow stress of LM25 metal was only slightly less than for LM0/9 Saf composite.

The composite materials were found to have limited workability, as evidenced by the formation of cracks on the cylindrical surfaces of samples deformed by as little as 8%. The cracking appeared to be much the same for LM0 and LM25 composites and was not affected significantly by forging temperature. However, use of PTFE lubrication between sample and platen was found to reduce markedly the extent of cracking, Figure 4.

3.2. Flexural Modulus

The flexural modulus of as-received LM0/20 Saf and LM25/20 Saf was established as 98 ± 8 GPa and 103 ± 8 GPa respectively. A deformation of 12% at room temperature reduced the modulus of both composites to ~ 80 GPa and this remained much the same up to a temperature of $\sim 450^{\circ}\text{C}$, Figure 5. Thereafter, with higher forging temperature the modulus of the composites tended towards the as-received value, reaching ~ 100 GPa at 625°C for LM0/20 Saf and at 550°C for LM25/20 Saf.

3.3. Microstructural Changes

3.3.1. Fibre Characteristics

The most notable feature of forged composites was fibre breakage, which was apparent after deformations of less than 5% at room temperature. With higher forging temperatures, the extent of breakage was markedly reduced, as evidenced by the mean fibre aspect ratio data presented in Figure 6. The formation of voids between the ends of broken fibres resulted in an increase in porosity, which amounted to $\sim 1.0\%$ for LM0/20 Saf and $\sim 1.9\%$ for LM25/20 Saf after a 12% deformation at 20°C . Less porosity was present in samples forged at higher temperatures.

Fibres in as-received LM0/9 Saf were found to have an almost random distribution of in-plane angle α , Figure 7a, but the out-of-plane angle β showed an increase in frequency at small angles, Figure 8a. These results are indicative of an approximately planar random fibre orientation, with a mean out-of-plane angle of $\sim 21^{\circ}$.

Fibre orientation was investigated for samples deformed by 12% and 60% at 625°C . The distribution of in-plane angle, measured relative to the radial direction ($\alpha=0$) showed no systematic trend with increased deformation, Figure 7. However, a preferred orientation was revealed in the histograms of out-of-plane angle, Figure 8. After a deformation of 12%, the average out-of-plane angle was $\sim 16^{\circ}$, slightly smaller than the value of $\sim 21^{\circ}$ obtained for as-received composite. The mean value decreased to $\sim 9^{\circ}$ after a deformation of 60%.

3.3.2. Matrix Microstructure

The LM0 composites were found to contain some regions of unreinforced matrix, presumably as a result of preform fracture during fabrication. After forging, such regions were deformed and

elongated in the direction of flow. Where matrix metal emerged at the cylindrical surface, considerable strain could be accommodated without fracture, Figure 9, although adjacent reinforced material was heavily cracked. The LM25/20 Saf composite, which did not exhibit regions of unreinforced matrix metal, contained a network of rod-like silicon particles.

TEM studies of as-received LM25/20 Saf revealed considerable dislocation activity throughout the matrix. More dislocations were apparent near fibre surfaces, Figure 10a, with many of the dislocation lines running into the fibre/matrix interface. The average dislocation density was found to be $3.1 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$.

After a deformation of 12% at room temperature the matrix of LM25/20 Saf had a well-developed cell structure, Figure 10b, with an average cell diameter of $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$. Extensive dislocation tangles within the cells were found to have a density of $5.5 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. After forging at 350°C , larger subgrains were observed with a mean diameter of $\sim 3.2 \mu\text{m}$ and a dislocation density of $2.3 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. Forging at 500°C resulted in a subgrain size of $\sim 3.7 \mu\text{m}$ and a dislocation structure around fibres which was similar to that found in as-received composite, with a density of $2.7 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Fibre Breakage and Orientation

Fibre breakage occurred at relatively small deformations ($<5\%$) during room temperature forging and resulted in fibres being broken some four times along their length. At higher forging temperatures, breakage was much reduced and, at temperatures close to the matrix melting point, approximately half the fibres were broken. In a previous paper³ we have related such a trend to a decrease in matrix flow stress with increase in temperature such that load transfer from matrix to fibre is reduced.

Measurement of fibre in-plane angle α for LM0/9 Saf showed no preferential alignment after deformations of 12% and 60%, Figure 7. Considering an element of the cylinder during deformation, see Figure 11, circumferential strains, ϵ_c , and radial strains, ϵ_r , are equal for homogeneous deformation⁵ and thus little change would be expected in the initial random alignment of fibres. However, the samples were forged without lubrication and this would have caused non-homogeneous deformation such that $\epsilon_r > \epsilon_c$, thereby tending to align fibres in the radial direction. Since such an effect was not apparent in the experimental data, the difference in the strains must have been relatively small.

With increased deformation, the fibre out-of-plane angle β tended to decrease such that fibres were more closely planar random, with the average out-of-plane angle for as-received composite ($\sim 21^\circ$) reduced to $\sim 16^\circ$ after 12% deformation and to $\sim 9^\circ$ after 60% deformation. Clearly, fibres are rotated during forging in response to the compressive normal strain (ϵ_n) and the tensile strains (ϵ_r and ϵ_c) so as to become more aligned in the direction of metal flow.

4.2. Matrix Microstructure

The dislocation density in as-received LM25/20 Saf of $3.1 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ corresponds to a plastic strain of $\sim 0.5\%$, and this is attributable to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (ΔCTE) between fibre and matrix⁶. After a 12% deformation at 20°C , a cell structure had formed and the dislocation density was increased to $5.5 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. However, the samples forged at 350°C had a smaller dislocation density ($2.3 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$) and a larger mean subgrain size ($\sim 3.2 \mu\text{m}$),

both of which are indicative of dynamic recovery during forging. The slight increase in dislocation density to $2.7 \pm 1.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ after forging at 500°C may have been due to the generation of dislocations during cooling from the forging temperature in response to the ΔCTE .

4.3. Flow Stress

Room temperature flow stress data, Figure 2, indicated that the addition of Saffil fibres or silicon particles (with volume fractions of $\sim 9\%$ and $\sim 8\%$ respectively) increased the flow stress and rate of work hardening of aluminium to a similar degree. Microstructural studies of the fibre composite revealed that severe fibre breakage occurred at room temperature. Thus it follows that the contribution to flow stress as a result of load transfer from matrix to fibre would have been small. It may be argued, therefore, that the similar increase in flow stress of LM0/9 Saf and LM25 compared with LM0 was due to dislocation pile-ups at fibre surfaces or silicon particles.

With higher forging temperature, the work hardening rate decreased and the flow stress of LM0/9 Saf and LM25 approached that obtained for LM0, see Figure 3. These trends may be attributed to an increased rate of dislocation climb, such that the fibres or silicon particles were less effective as barriers to the movement of dislocations. Indeed, by $\sim 300^\circ\text{C}$ all materials exhibited a constant flow stress, indicating that the rate of work hardening was balanced by the rate of dynamic recovery. At high temperature, despite the reduced fibre breakage, contributions to the flow stress arising from load transfer to fibres is again expected to be small, since the matrix flow stress is low.

4.4. Workability

Composite materials forged without lubrication exhibited extensive surface cracking, with little difference in behaviour between LM0 and LM25 matrices or with increase in forging temperature. These results indicate that workability was controlled by the fibres rather than the ductility of the matrix. Thus it is argued that the formation of voids, especially between the ends of broken fibres, was the major cause for the initiation of fracture in response to tensile stresses introduced as a result of surface barrelling⁵. The apparently uncracked surface of the sample forged with PTFE lubrication may be attributed to the absence of surface tensile stresses, since no barrelling had occurred.

The heavily deformed regions of matrix metal observed at the surface of LM0 composites, Figure 9, suggests that workability could be usefully improved by incorporating a surface layer of unreinforced matrix.

4.5. Flexural Modulus

The flexural modulus of as-received LM0/20 Saf and LM25/20 Saf were $\sim 98 \text{ GPa}$ and $\sim 103 \text{ GPa}$ respectively. After forging at room temperature, the values were reduced by $\sim 20\%$ and remained much the same up to forging temperatures of $\sim 450^\circ\text{C}$, after which they tended towards as-received values. These results can be related to the microstructural damage, specifically fibre breakage and porosity, introduced during the forging process. Thus, in samples forged at room temperature, the smaller fibre aspect ratio would reduce flexural modulus because a greater proportion of the fibre length is then not fully loaded. In addition, porosity increases of $\sim 1.0\%$ and $\sim 1.9\%$ for LM0/20 Saf and LM25/20 Saf would significantly reduce flexural rigidity, especially as the voids were formed at fibre surfaces. The increase in modulus with higher forging temperature may thus be attributed to a decrease in porosity and the extent of fibre breakage.

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Figure 1. (a) Planar random fibre orientation, (b) in-plane angle α , (c) out-of-plane angle β .

Figure 2. Flow stress curves for (a) unreinforced LM0, (b) unreinforced LM25 and (c) LM0/9 Saf.

Figure 3. Flow stress at a strain of 10% as a function of forging temperature.

Figure 4. The effect of lubrication on surface cracking of LM0/9 Saf; (a) forged without lubrication, (b) forged with PTFE lubrication.

Figure 5. The effect of forging temperature on flexural modulus.
 ▼ LM0/20 Saf □ LM25/20 Saf
 Arrows indicate as-received values.

Figure 6. The effect of forging temperature on mean fibre aspect ratio.
 ▼ LM0/20 Saf ■ LM25/20 Saf
 Arrows indicate as-received values.

Figure 7. In-plane angle α for LM0/9 Saf; (a) as-received, (b) 12% deformation, (c) 60% deformation.

Figure 8. Out-of-plane angle β (a) as-received, (b) 12% deformation, (c) 60% deformation.

Figure 9. Fibre-free matrix and surface cracks in forged LM0/9 Saf.

Figure 10. LM25/20 Saf; (a) undeformed and (b) 12% deformed at 20°C

Figure 11. An element of the composite during deformation.

